

Relation between fatigue life and tensile strength of wood plastic composites

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Abstract

Wood plastic composite (WPC) is a composite material made of wood fibers and plastic matrix, resulting in supplementing mutual drawbacks. Because of high stiffness of cellulose contained in wood fibers, WPC is expected as a practical structural material. In this study, we aimed to clarify the relation between tensile strength and fatigue life of the WPC materials. Firstly, the effects of different wood fiber amount and dispersibility on the properties of WPC were studied (denoted as Study A). In order to investigate the influence of dispersibility, pellets with one or two kneading processes were prepared. Secondly, the influence of milling time to wood fibers on properties of WPC was investigated (denoted as Study B). Tensile and fatigue tests were carried out for each type of specimen. As for Study A result, both tensile strength and fatigue life of WPC specimens are found to be significantly higher than those of PP specimen. It is understood that the tensile strength of specimens with two kneading processes increases as compared with one process. From the obtained result of Study B, the highest value of tensile strength and fatigue life can be confirmed at 1 hour of milling time. In addition, after 2 hours of milling time, both tensile strength and fatigue life start to decrease due to decreasing in size of wood fiber with the increase of milling time. Moreover, it should be noted from the correlation coefficients that, there is a strong correlation between the tensile strength and the fatigue life especially in the case of Study A.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have become an appropriate alternative medium that can be applied instead of the conventional single materials used in many industries. This is because composite materials offer wide range of advantages such as high durability, light weight, high stiffness and low maintenance. Moreover, the composite properties can be directed to the desired properties that suit the application by selecting two or more appropriate constituents. When taking account of composite materials from, the environmentally friendly point of view, natural fiber-reinforced composite materials, or known as *green composites* can be selected as one of the most appropriate materials, by combining bio-based

fillers with a biodegradable resin or minimizing the use of petroleum-derived materials such as polymer by incorporating the natural-based reinforcements into the polymeric matrix [1]. Although there are many biomass-based resources available, wood fibers are compatible as a filler of *green composites* because of its ease of availability and low production cost.

Whereas single wood materials have been used in many products such as household articles, furniture and other interior items for centuries, wood plastic composite (WPC) is a composite material made of wood fibers and plastic matrix, resulting in supplementing mutual drawbacks. Because of the high stiffness of cellulose contained in wood fibers [2], WPC is expected as a secondary structural material, applied for machine parts, such as car interior parts. In recent years, WPC attracts many attentions from the industries and academics due to its excellent properties and performances. These include studies on various mechanical properties of WPC, such as tensile [3-4], impact [5-6], fatigue [7] properties and many others. Thus, in this study, we aimed to focus on the relation between tensile strength and fatigue life of the WPC materials from the viewpoint of reliability engineering.

2. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

In this study, we focus on two case studies regarding the effect on the mechanical properties of WPC. First study is the effect of wood fiber content and dispersibility, and another is its size.

2.1 Preparation of WPC specimens

2.2.1 Study A In this study, we studied the effects of different wood fiber amount and dispersibility on the properties of WPC. Master-batch (Cellbrid-N, TOCLAS Co., Ltd.) was mixed with polypropylene (PP, Prime Polymer Co., Ltd.) to produce WPC specimen. Master-batch contains 70wt% wood fiber with the average length of 140 μm and 30wt% PP. Hereinafter, the WPC and virgin PP specimens are referred as WF/PP and Neat PP, respectively. Four different types of the WF/PP specimens are prepared, which are named as Neat PP, 30%WF/PP, and 50%WF/PP (30% and 50% mean fiber contents in weight), respectively. Master-batch and PP were kneaded by single screw extruder (Musashino Kikai Co., Ltd.). In order to investigate the influence of dispersibility, WF/PP mixture pellets were prepared through one or two times kneading processes. The number of the kneading process is denoted at the end of the specimen name. The mixture pellets were molded into a dumbbell shape specimen with the dimensions of 3mm width, 2mm thickness and 18mm gauge length by an injection molding machine (Imoto Machinery Co., Ltd.). Shape and dimension of the specimen is shown in Figure 1.

2.1.2 Study B In Study B, the influence of wood fiber size on properties of WPC was investigated. Wood fibers were directly milled in a planetary ball (Fritsch Japan Co., Ltd.) with rotational speed of 200 rpm. It was milled for 30 min, 1 hr, 2 hr, 4 hr and 8 hr. The milled wood fibers were then mixed with polypropylene (PP, Prime Polymer Co., Ltd.) and a compatibilizer, maleated anhydride PP (MAPP, Kayaku Akzo Co., Ltd.), to produce WPC specimen. These materials were mixed by labo plastomill (Toyoseiki Co., Ltd.) with 30 rpm rotation speed at 190 °C. In Study B, the fiber content

was 25% for the all specimens prepared. The milling time is denoted at the end of the specimen name. The mixture was molded into a dumbbell shape specimen with the same dimensions as Study A by injection molding (babyplast 6/10P, I O M Co., Ltd.).

Figure 1 Shape and dimension of WPC specimen (Unit: mm)

2.2 Tensile and fatigue tests

Tensile and fatigue tests were carried out for each type of specimen by electro-hydraulic precision materials testing machine (Shimadzu Co., Ltd.) at room temperature. As test condition of tensile test, cross head speed was 10 mm/min. As test condition of fatigue test, the followings were given: Applied load: 90, 80, 70, or 60 % level of tensile strength, Stress ratio: 0.1, Frequency: 3.5 Hz. The conditions were applied until the failure occurs.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 Study A

The results of tensile and fatigue tests are shown in Figure 2. The average values of the tensile properties are shown in Table 1. From these results, it is found that both tensile strength and fatigue life of WPC specimens are significantly higher than those of Neat PP specimen. It is also understood from the comparison of 30% WF/PP that both tensile strength and fatigue life of specimens with two kneading processes are slightly higher than one process. This is an expected result due to the improvement of dispersibility by more kneading processes.

(a) Typical tensile stress-strain curves

(b) S-N diagrams

Figure 2 Tensile and fatigue results of Study A (-1 and -2 mean the number of kneading)

Table 1 Tensile properties of Study A

	Tensile strength [MPa]	Strain at break [%]	Young's modulus [GPa]
Neat PP	34.1	Unbroken	0.340
25% WF/PP-1	38.9	-	-
30% WF/PP-1	40.9	11.5	0.427
50% WF/PP-1	47.3	11.6	0.448
30% WF/PP-2	42.2	13.1	0.414
50% WF/PP-2	47.0	12.4	0.527

3.2 Study B

The results of tensile and fatigue test are shown in Figure 3, respectively. The average values of the tensile strength are shown in Table 2. That the unpulverized specimens in Study B (25%WF/PP-0hr) could be compared with the data of Study A, since the tensile strength of 25% WF/PP-0hr is 38.9 MPa. From the obtained result of Study B, the highest value of tensile strength and fatigue life can be confirmed at 1 hour milling time. In addition, after 1 hour milling time, both tensile strength and fatigue life start to decrease due to decreasing in size of wood fiber with increase in milling time. This is because smaller wood fiber has higher tendency to form agglomerates, resulting in decrease in the properties of the composites. Thus, the tensile and fatigue properties are improved as the wood fiber contents increased, and approximately 1 hour is estimated as the appropriate time to pulverize the wood fiber finely.

Figure 3 The results of Study B (The fiber content is 25wt%)

Table 2 The average tensile strength of Study B (Unit:MPa)

25% WF/PP						
0hr	30min	1hr	2hr	4hr	8hr	
38.9	40.2	40.3	37.9	34.5	34.0	

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Correlation coefficients

From the results of Studies A and B, the same trend was found for the relation between tensile strength and fatigue life such that, when the tensile strength is high, the fatigue life is also high. So, the correlation coefficients are calculated and shown in Table 3. Table 3 also shows tensile strength obtained from both Studies A and B, and slope / intercept values from the linearly approximated S-N curve of fatigue life. It should be noted from the correlation coefficients in Table 3 that, there is a strong correlation between the tensile strength and the fatigue life as these all values are close to unity, especially in the case of Study A. Similar tendency of correlation coefficient is also known for metal materials [8] such as aluminum and steel, and also for fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) material. That means, it is newly found out in this study that WPC also tends to have the similar relation.

Table 3 Correlation coefficients between the tensile strength and the fatigue life

	Tensile Strength [MPa]	S-N curve* ¹		Correlation coefficient* ²			
		Slope	Intercept	25 [MPa]	30 [MPa]	35 [MPa]	
Study A	Neat PP	34.1	-2.09	34.5	-	-	-
	25% WF/PP-1	38.9	-3.15	38.5			
	30% WF/PP-1	40.9	-3.19	42.2			
	50% WF/PP-1	47.3	-3.56	47.6	0.971	0.982	0.990
	30% WF/PP-2	42.2	-3.29	44.0			
	50% WF/PP-2	47.0	-3.67	48.1			
Study B	25% WF/PP-0hr	38.9	-3.15	38.5			
	25% WF/PP-30min	40.2	-3.21	39.4			
	25% WF/PP-1hr	40.3	-3.18	40.4	0.781	0.798	0.818
	25% WF/PP-2hr	37.9	-2.65	36.6			
	25% WF/PP-4hr	34.5	-2.77	33.8			
	25% WF/PP-8hr	34.0	-2.78	32.8			

*1 Linear approximation on semi-logarithmic scale

*2 Coefficients between tensile strengths and cross points of applied stress and S-N approximation line
The number of kneading and the milling time are denoted at the end of the specimen name.

5. CONCLUSION

In this study, we aimed to clarify the relation between tensile strength and fatigue life of the WPC materials. Firstly, the effects of different wood fiber amount and dispersibility on the properties of WPC were studied (denoted as Study A). Secondly, the influence of milling time to wood fibers on WPC properties was investigated (denoted as Study B).

(1) From the results of Study A, both tensile strength and fatigue life of WPC specimens are found to be significantly higher than those of Neat PP specimen. It is understood that both tensile strength and

fatigue life of 30wt% fiber content specimens with two kneading processes increases as compared with one process. This is an expected result due to the improvement of dispersibility by more kneading processes.

(2) From the result of Study B, the highest value of tensile strength and fatigue life can be confirmed at 1 hour of milling time. In addition, after 1 hour, both tensile strength and fatigue life start to decrease due to decreasing in size of wood fiber with milling time. This is because smaller wood fiber has higher tendency to form aggregates, resulting in decrease in the properties of the composites.

(3) From the results of Studies A and B, it is concluded that there is a strong correlation between the tensile strength and the fatigue life as the almost all values are in the range of 0.8 to 1.0. Similar tendency of correlation coefficient is also known for metal materials such as aluminum, steel material and also for fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) material. That means, it is newly found out in this study that WPC also tends to have the similar relation.

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